

AWARENESS OF HUMAN RIGHTS AMONG ENGINEERING STUDENTS**Dr. Dandinker Suryakant N.**

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Abstract

The human right awareness is important for present society in which people of different castes, creeds, religion and cultures live together. Our constitution bestowed some rights i.e. respect for human dignity and social integrity. Even basic human rights concepts, which are integrated in education systems. The numbers of students are higher education in our country. The researchers aim to study the significance of human rights awareness about engineering students. Thus the researchers thought for doing an investigation to ensure the awareness regarding human rights. Indian education incorporated human rights are the part of our curriculum. After this survey the research find out engineering students awareness about human rights. The survey was conducted on 100, engineering students in engineering colleges in Chikkamagalur. The Self developed tool was applied for the study and 't' technique was adopted to analyzes the data. The result shows awareness of human rights among girls engineering students is less than boys and rural boys and girls are more aware than urban boys & girls. The implication of the study engineering students has less awareness about human rights. So engineering colleges must conduct various human rights awareness programme and enhance the awareness.

Keywords— *Human rights, Awareness, Eengineering students, Chikkamagalu*

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Introduction

The human right are an instrument for promotes equality, social justice and respect for the individual human being in the society. Human rights are inherent in nature and refer to the fundamental freedoms and basic liberties without which humans cannot live with respect and dignity. We all live in a society and all our activities revolve round this societal system.

People's rights are regulated by rule of law and it is the duty of the government to enforce and protect these rights irrespective of their caste, creed, race, sex, religion and place of birth. Education for human rights is an important aspect for obligation to further universal respect for justice, the rule of law and human rights. The curriculum framework prescribed for incorporate human rights programmes for promotes awareness the students.

Signification of the Study

The concept of human rights has been accepted global value for person. The young students are discussing daily issues, and become aware of issues associated with human dignity and rights. Human rights education upholds the respect for human dignity, rights, justice, tolerance, cooperation, social responsibility, and respect for cultural diversity, additionally to a firm commitment to democracy and non-violent conflict resolution. The most concern of human rights is equality, social justice and peace in society. Basic to human rights are the values of non-discrimination and equality, which contribute for building a culture of peace in society. The modern society isn't giving importance of spiritual and moral values of the society. The diverse information's accessed through media influences impressionistic minds of young students and makes them to unaware of the responsibilities and human rights. The students should know or aware of human rights. After the completion of their courses, they will enter into the society and will involve in different social, political roles and responsibilities. Unless and until they would learn and understand human rights they cannot access them properly. That they can be used whenever there is discrimination on the grounds of sex, race, color, descent, national or ethnic origin or religious belief or Based on class or caste systems in modern times. Therefore, researchers aim to review the significance of human rights awareness to the engineering students. After this survey the researcher find out engineering students awareness about human rights.

Objective of the Study

1. To find out the significant difference between engineering students awareness on human rights with respect to gender.
2. To find out the significant difference between engineering students awareness on human rights with respect to demographic

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between engineering students' awareness about human rights with respect to Gender.
2. There is no significant difference engineering students' awareness about human rights with respect to demographic.

Review of Literature

VimalKumar et al. (2014) studied about awareness of human rights' among B.Ed student teacher in Punducharry. The study was an attempt to study the awareness of human rights of B.Ed. student teachers. Sample sizes are 300 student teachers were taken from Punducharry region. The data has been collected through questionnaire and normative survey method has been adopted by the investigator to achieve the objectives of the study. Both the descriptive and differential analysis is carried out. The finding suggested that awareness of human rights of B.Ed. student teachers is found to be low level.

Sushma Rani Hooda et al. (2018) 'A study of human rights awareness among B.Ed. College students of Sirsa district of Haryana state' researcher taken 100 B.Ed samples and descriptive survey method was used. Result of the study is Private B.Ed. College students is more than Human Rights of University maintained B.Ed. college students. Urban B.Ed. students are more than Human Rights of rural B.Ed. students' urban female students are more than rural female B.Ed. students.

Dr. Dandinker Suryakant N (2019) 'The survey was conducted on 200, Science and commerce degree students in different Colleges of Chikkamagalur town. The Self developed tool was applied for the study and 't' technique was adopted to analyses the data. The result shows overall awareness of human rights among science degree students lesser than the commerce degree students. But science degree students have more awareness on civil, social, cultural, economic, political, international rights awareness science degree students than commerce degree students. Respect to the gender science degree male and female students is more aware than commerce degree male and female students.

Dr. Dandinker Suryakant N (2019) the survey was conducted on 100, nursing students in different nursing Colleges of Chikkamagalur. The Self developed tool was applied for the study and 't' technique was adopted to analyzes the data. The result shows awareness of human

rights among girls nursing students is less than boys and rural boys and girls are more aware than urban boys & girls. The implication of the study nursing students has less awareness about human rights. So nursing colleges must conduct various human rights awareness programme and enhance the awareness.

Research Methodology

Sample: The present research is a survey method in nature. It is conducted in Chikkamagalur town of Karnataka. The total sample was consisted 100; this sample includes 50 boys and 50 girls' students among 50 students 25 student urban 25 rural students of Chikkamagalur town.

Tools: The survey method is adopted. A Human Rights Awareness Questionnaire (HRAQ) developed by the investigator was used for data collection. The HRAQ consists of 30 YES/NO statement, yes for 1 mark & No for Zero Marks will be awarded. The questionnaire covers basic issues such as articles in UDHR.

Statistical Techniques for Data Analyses: The researcher adopted Statistical techniques viz. Mean, S.D., Critical Ratio (t-test for data analyses).

Limitation: The researcher was conducted study only on those who are studying Engineering in Chikkamagalur town.

Results and Discussion

The research analysis of awareness of human rights among engineering students by objective wise.

Data Based Description Of Objective: -1 to find out the significant difference between engineering students' awareness on human rights with respect to gender.

Table 1 Human Rights Awareness of Engineering Students.

Variable	N	M	SD	M.df	t	p
Boys	50	24.22	1.69	2.06*	5.20	1.99
Girls	50	22.16	2.18			

* Significant Different at 0.05 levels

The above table-1 shows that There is a significant different between awareness on human rights among boys & Girls Engineering students. The calculated t exceeds the critical value, so the means are significantly different. Thus the hypothesis is rejected.

Data based description of objective: 2. there is no significant difference engineering students' awareness about human rights with respect to demographic.

Table-2. Human rights awareness of urban boys & girls engineering students.

Variable	N	M	SD	M.df	t	p
Urban Boys	25	22.44	2.47	0.92*	1.16	2.011
Rural Girls	25	21.52	3.14			

*Not Significant difference at $p < 0.05$

The above table-2 shows that There is not significant different between awareness on human rights among urban boys & girls engineering students. The calculated t value is smaller than critical value, so the means are not significantly different. Therefore the hypothesis is rejected.

Table-3. Human rights Awareness of rural boys and girls engineering students.

Variable	N	M	SD	M.df	t	p
Rural Boys	25	24.4	2.13	1.56*	2.42	2.011
Rural Girls	25	22.84	2.45			

*Significant Difference at $p < 0.05$

The above table-3 shows that There is a significant different between awareness on human rights among rural boys & girls engineering students. The calculated t exceeds the critical value, so the means are significantly different. Thus the hypothesis is rejected.

Table-4. Human rights Awareness of urban boys and rural boys engineering students

Variable	N	M	SD	M.df	t	p
Urban Boys	25	22.44	2.47	-1.96*	-3.012	2.011
Rural boys	25	24.4	2.13			

* Significant Difference at $p < 0.05$

The above table-4 shows that There is a significant different between awareness on human rights among urban boys & rural boys engineering students. The calculated t value is lesser than the critical value, so the means are significantly different. Thus the hypothesis is rejected

Table-5. Human rights awareness of urban girls and rural girls engineering students

Variable	N	M	SD	M.df	t	p
Urban girls	25	21.52	3.14	-1.32*	-1.66	2.011
Rural Girls	25	22.84	2.45			

*Not significant at $p < 0.05$

The above table-5 shows that there is no significant different between awareness on human rights among urban girls & rural girls' engineering students the calculated 't' is smaller than critical value, so the means are not significantly different.

Main Finding of the Study

- The mean value of human rights awareness of engineering students is more than the girls' students. Thus, the boys engineering students are more aware than girls engineering students.
- The mean value of human rights awareness of engineering urban boys and rural girls' students not significant. Thus, human rights of engineering urban boys and rural girls are aware human rights.
- The mean value of human rights awareness of engineering rural boys' students is more than the rural girls' students. Thus, the rural boys engineering students are more aware than rural boys engineering students.
- The mean value of human rights awareness of engineering urban boys' students is lesser than the rural boys' engineering students. Thus, the rural boys engineering students are more aware than urban boys engineering students.
- The mean value of human rights awareness of engineering urban girls' students is lesser than the rural girls' engineering students. Thus, the rural girls engineering students are more aware than urban girls engineering students.

Conclusion

The researcher has under taken mainly to find out what proportion of the engineering students possess awareness on human rights on the basis of finding that noticed only negligible proportion of the population shown high awareness. The survey result is shows there is an urgent need to initiate action and must conduct awareness comps make them students aware about human rights. Human rights education is a significant aspect to bring the peace and harmony in society. Without equity, liberty, and justice, dignity it is impossible to promote and cultivate the peace, tolerance, and harmony in the society.

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